

Motivational Climate and Achievement Goal Orientation in Youth Sport: The Differential Roles of Parents, Coaches, and Peers

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Abstract: *Background: Achievement Goal Theory posits that perceived motivational climate shaped by significant social agents substantially influences how young athletes conceptualize success and pursue athletic goals. Despite extensive research in Western contexts, the relative contributions of parents, coaches, and peers to achievement goal orientation among college-level athletes in South Asian settings remain underexplored.*

Objective: This study examined the associations and predictive effects of parental, coaching, and peer motivational climates on task and ego achievement goal orientations among male college athletes in Lahore, Pakistan.

Methods: A quantitative cross-sectional survey design was employed. A proportionate random sample of 90 male student-athletes (Mage = 18.6, SD = 0.45) was drawn from five government colleges in Lahore District. Four validated instruments the Task and Ego Orientation in Sport Questionnaire (TEOSQ), Parent-Initiated Motivational Climate Questionnaire-2 (PIMCQ-2), and Motivational Climate Scale for Youth Sport (MCSYS), and Peer Motivational Climate in Youth Sport Questionnaire (PMCYSQ) were administered. Data were analyzed using Pearson correlation, multiple regression, independent samples t-test, and one-way ANOVA ($\alpha = .05$).

Results: Peer motivational climate demonstrated a strong, statistically significant positive association with achievement goal orientation ($r = .843, p < .001$) and emerged as the dominant predictor ($\beta = .847, p < .001$), explaining 73.4% of the total variance ($R^2 = .734$) in the combined regression model. Parental and coaching motivational climates yielded weak, non-significant correlations with achievement goal orientation. Sport type (coaches' and peers' climate) and college affiliation (parents' climate and achievement goals) produced significant subgroup differences.

Conclusion: Peers constitute the most influential social agent for achievement goal formation among collegiate youth athletes in this context, surpassing the contributions of parents and coaches. Findings underscore the need for peer centered motivational interventions and structured coach and parent education programs to cultivate adaptive goal orientations in youth sport.

Keywords: *Achievement Goal Theory; motivational climate; youth sport; peer influence; coach–athlete relationship; parental influence; task orientation; ego orientation*

Introduction

The sporting environment inherently frames success in competitive terms, and young athletes continuously interpret cues from their social surroundings to evaluate their own competence and define what it means to achieve. Achievement Goal Theory (AGT; Ames, 1992; Nicholls, 1989) provides a robust framework for understanding how these social perceptions translate into distinct motivational orientations specifically, task orientation (mastery-focused, self-referential standards of success) and ego orientation (normative comparison and outperforming peers). A central premise of AGT is that the motivational climate established by key social agents parents, coaches, and peers profoundly shape which goal orientation an athlete adopts.

Research consistently documents that parents are influential gatekeepers of early sport participation, with their attitudes and behaviors shaping children's self-perceptions of athletic ability, intrinsic motivation, and continued engagement (Fredricks & Eccles, 2004; O'Rourke et al., 2014). Coaches, as the primary authority figures within the training environment, determine the structural and evaluative conditions under which athletes strive, and their emphases on mastery or normative comparison have been associated with differential psychological outcomes (Smith et al., 2008). Peers, particularly as athletes' progress through adolescence, assume increasing importance as sources of social comparison, belonging, and motivational influence (Keegan et al., 2010; Vazou et al., 2005).

Despite considerable scholarship in Western contexts, very limited research has examined how these three social agents simultaneously and differentially predict achievement goal orientations among youth athletes in South Asian settings. The motivational landscape in Pakistani collegiate sport is particularly unexplored, despite representing an important developmental period for athletic identity formation. College-level student-athletes face unique pressures from institutional environments, family expectations, and peer cultures that may render the relative influence of parents, coaches, and peers distinct from patterns observed in Western samples.

Furthermore, the preponderance of existing studies has relied on cross-sectional, single-source designs that preclude simultaneous comparison of the three social agents (Harwood et al., 2015). The present investigation addresses these gaps by employing a multi-source measurement strategy to assess parental-, coaching-, and peer-initiated motivational climates concurrently and to determine their unique predictive contributions to achievement goal orientation. The findings are intended to inform targeted intervention strategies for coaches, sport psychologists, and institutional administrators seeking to optimize the motivational environments of college-level athletes.

METHODS

Research Design and Participants

A quantitative cross-sectional survey design was adopted. The target population comprised male student-athletes competing in intercollegiate sport events across five government colleges in Lahore District, Pakistan (N = 889). Using proportionate random

sampling, 10% of each college's athletic population was selected, yielding a final sample of 90 participants (Mage = 18.6 years, SD = 0.45; range = 16–24 years). All participants were actively registered and competing across seven sports (cricket, football, volleyball, badminton, table tennis, hockey, and athletics). Written consent was obtained from all participants, and institutional permissions were secured from both the university and each participating college prior to data collection.

Instruments

Achievement Goal Orientation (Dependent Variable). The Task and Ego Orientation in Sport Questionnaire (TEOSQ; Duda & Nicholls, 1992) consists of 13 items that assess athletes' conceptions of success in sport through a task-oriented (7 items) and ego-oriented (6 items) subscale. Responses are scored on a five-point Likert scale anchored at 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The instrument demonstrated strong internal reliability in the current sample ($\alpha = .876$).

Parental Motivational Climate. The Parent-Initiated Motivational Climate Questionnaire-2 (PIMCQ-2; White & Duda, 1993) captures athletes' perceptions of the motivational climate established by both mother and father across three subscales each (task-involving and ego-involving dimensions). Internal consistency estimates for the present sample were acceptable across all subscales (α range: .733–.836).

Coaching Motivational Climate. The Motivational Climate Scale for Youth Sport (MCSYS; Smith et al., 2008), a 12-item scale, assessed the degree to which coaches fostered task-mastery versus ego-involving climates. The scale employs a five-point Likert format and has demonstrated sound psychometric properties in youth sporting populations.

Peer Motivational Climate. The Peer Motivational Climate in Youth Sport Questionnaire (PMCYSQ; Ntoumanis & Vazou, 2005) is a 21-item instrument measuring five dimensions of peer climate: task improvement, relatedness support, effort emphasis, intra-team competition/ability, and intra-team conflict.

Procedure

Following receipt of all institutional permissions and questionnaire author approvals via email correspondence, the researcher administered the battery of instruments through personal site visits to each college. Participants were provided a standardized briefing on the purpose of the study, assured of anonymity, and given up to one week to complete the questionnaires at their convenience. Of the 120 questionnaires distributed (a deliberate over-distribution to account for attrition), 90 completed, usable responses were returned, representing a 100% usable return rate from the target sample.

Statistical Analysis

All data were entered and analyzed using SPSS Version 26. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, and variance) characterized sample and variable distributions. Pearson correlation coefficients examined bivariate associations between motivational climate variables and achievement goal orientation. Multiple regression analysis determined

the unique predictive contribution of each social agent's climate to achievement goal orientation. Independent samples t-tests compared achievement goal orientation and motivational climate scores across sport type (individual vs. team) and parental sports background (athlete vs. non-athlete). One-way ANOVA examined differences across college affiliation, age group, sport experience, and sport discipline. The significance threshold was set at $\alpha = .05$.

RESULTS

Sample Characteristics

The sample comprised athletes across seven sports: cricket (n = 22, 24.4%), football (n = 20, 22.2%), volleyball (n = 17, 18.9%), athletics (n = 11, 12.2%), badminton (n = 7, 7.8%), table tennis (n = 7, 7.8%), and hockey (n = 6, 6.7%). The majority competed in team sports (n = 55, 61.1%) compared to individual sports (n = 35, 38.9%). In terms of experience, 50% had 4–5 years of competitive sport experience, 26.7% had six or more years, and 23.3% had fewer than three years. With respect to age, 60% fell in the 19–20 year range, 27.8% were 21 years or older and 12.2% was aged 16–18. Fifty-five percent of participants reported having parents with no prior athletic background.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for all study variables. Mean scores across all three motivational climate variables and achievement goal orientation fell in the moderate-to-moderate-high range (3.24–3.54 on a five-point scale), indicating generally positive perceptions of social motivational environments.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics for Study Variables (N = 90)

Variable	N	M	SD	Variance
Parental Motivational Climate	90	3.24	0.98	0.97
Coaching Motivational Climate	90	3.54	0.52	0.27
Peer Motivational Climate	90	3.46	0.68	0.47
Achievement Goal Orientation	90	3.53	0.63	0.40

Note. M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation. All variables measured on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree).

Bivariate Associations (Hypothesis 1)

Table 2 presents the Pearson correlation matrix. The association between peer motivational climate and achievement goal orientation was strong and statistically significant ($r = .843, p < .001$), constituting by far the strongest bivariate relationship in the matrix. In contrast, parental motivational climate ($r = .197, p = .063$) and coaching motivational climate ($r = .026, p = .805$) demonstrated weak, non-significant correlations with achievement goal orientation. Hypothesis 1 was therefore partially supported: peer motivational climate was

significantly associated with achievement goal orientation, while parental and coaching climates were not.

Table 2

Pearson Correlation Matrix for Study Variables

Variable	1	2	3	4
1. Parental Motivational Climate	—			
2. Coaching Motivational Climate	.071	—		
3. Peer Motivational Climate	.107	.147	—	
4. Achievement Goal Orientation	.197	.026	.843	—

Note. $P < .01$ (two-tailed).

Predictive Effects of Motivational Climate (Hypothesis 2)

Multiple regression analysis (Table 3) revealed that the combined model explained a substantial proportion of variance in achievement goal orientation ($R = .857$, $R^2 = .734$, Adjusted $R^2 = .724$), and was statistically significant ($F[3, 86] = 78.94$, $p < .001$). Peer motivational climate emerged as the dominant and only statistically significant predictor ($\beta = .847$, $B = .786$, $p < .001$). Parental motivational climate exerted a small but significant independent effect ($\beta = .114$, $B = .073$, $p = .046$). Coaching motivational climate did not reach significance ($\beta = -.106$, $B = -.129$, $p = .064$), with its standardized coefficient suggesting a mild suppressive effect on achievement goal orientation within the model. Hypothesis 2 was supported: collectively, the three social agents' motivational climates significantly influenced achievement goal orientation, with peer climate constituting the dominant influence.

Table 3

Multiple Regressions: Prediction of Achievement Goal Orientation from Motivational Climate Variables

Predictor	B	SE B	β	t	p	95% CI
(Constant)	1.038	.295	-----	3.518	.001	[.452, 1.625]
Parental Climate	.073	.036	.114	2.026	.046	[.002, .145]
Coaching Climate	-.129	.069	.106	1.878	.064	[-.265, .008]
Peer Climate	.786	.052	.847	14.976	.000	[.682, .890]

Note. $R^2 = .734$; Adjusted $R^2 = .724$; $F(3, 86) = 78.94$, $p < .001$. $p < .05$. $p < .001$. CI = Confidence Interval.

Demographic Differences (Hypothesis 3)

Table 4 summarizes findings from one-way ANOVA and independent samples t-tests across demographic subgroups.

Table 4

Summary of Group Difference Analyses for Study Variables by Demographic Variables

Demographic	Outcome Variable	Test	F / t	df	p	Sig?
College (5 groups)	Parental Climate	ANOVA	F = 5.32	4, 85	.001	Yes
	Coaching Climate	ANOVA	F = 0.59	4, 85	.671	No
	Peer Climate	ANOVA	F = 0.95	4, 85	.441	No
	Achievement Goals	ANOVA	F = 2.74	4, 85	.034	Yes
Age (3 groups)	All Variables	ANOVA	F < 1.35	2, 87	>.270	No
Experience (3 groups)	All Variables	ANOVA	F < 2.40	2, 87	>.097	No
Sport Discipline (7 groups)	Parental Climate	ANOVA	F = 1.75	6, 83	.121	No
	Coaching Climate	ANOVA	F = 2.29	6, 83	.042	Yes
	Peer Climate	ANOVA	F = 2.36	6, 83	.038	Yes
	Achievement Goals	ANOVA	F = 2.30	6, 83	.032	Yes
Sport Type (Individual vs. Team)	All Variables	t-test	t < 1.27	88	>.207	No
Parental Background (Athlete vs. Non-athlete)	All Variables	t-test	t < 0.65	88	>.521	No

Note. $p < .05$. Significant college-level differences: parental climate was highest in Commerce College No. 2 ($M = 3.77$); achievement goal orientation was highest in GAC No. 1 ($M = 3.82$). Sport discipline differences driven by higher coaching climate among hockey players ($M = 3.92$), higher peer climate and achievement goal orientation among volleyball players ($M = 3.81$ and $M = 3.80$, respectively).

College affiliation produced significant group differences in parental motivational climate ($F[4, 85] = 5.32, p = .001$) and achievement goal orientation ($F[4, 85] = 2.74, p = .034$), but not in coaching or peer motivational climates. Sport discipline yielded significant differences in coaching motivational climate ($F[6, 83] = 2.29, p = .042$), peer motivational climate ($F[6, 83] = 2.36, p = .038$), and achievement goal orientation ($F[6, 83] = 2.30, p = .032$), but not in parental climate. Hockey athletes perceived the highest coaching climate ($M = 3.92$), while volleyball athletes reported the highest peer climate ($M = 3.81$) and achievement goal orientation scores ($M = 3.80$). Age, years of experience, sport type (team

vs. individual), and parental athletic background did not produce any significant group differences across any study variable. Hypothesis 3 was partially supported.

DISCUSSION

The primary objective of this investigation was to examine the relative contributions of parental, coaching, and peer motivational climates to achievement goal orientation in college-level youth athletes. Three findings warrant particular discussion.

First, and most prominently, peer motivational climate accounted for the overwhelming majority of explained variance in achievement goal orientation ($\beta = .847$, $R^2 = .734$), a finding consistent with developmental perspectives suggesting that peers progressively displace parents and even coaches as the dominant socializing force across late adolescence (Keegan et al., 2010, 2014). Adolescent athletes in the college-level specialization stage engage in intensive, daily contact with training peers, creating conditions for frequent normative comparison, collaborative skill refinement, and the transmission of effort norms. Vazou et al. (2005) documented 11 dimensions of peer climate in qualitative interviews with youth athletes, including task improvement, relatedness support, and effort emphasis each of which channels athletes toward either task- or ego-oriented achievement frameworks. The present findings extend those qualitative insights by quantifying the predictive dominance of peer climate across a contextually distinct sample.

Second, the negative though non-significant regression coefficient for coaching motivational climate ($\beta = -.106$, $p = .064$) is theoretically notable. While the raw bivariate correlation between coaching climate and achievement goal orientation was negligible ($r = .026$), its direction within the multivariate model suggests that the existing coach-created environment may not be functionally aligned with athletes' task or ego goal frameworks. One plausible interpretation is that coaching practices in the sampled colleges inadvertently create an ambiguous or inconsistent motivational environment neither clearly mastery-promoting nor performance-emphasizing that fails to meaningfully activate athletes' achievement goal schemas. This interpretation is consistent with Harwood et al.'s (2015) systematic review identifying substantial variability in the quality and intentionality of coach-created motivational climates. Alternatively, the negative coefficient could reflect that coaches' ego-involving behaviors (e.g., emphasis on winning, differential recognition) are counter-productive within a context where peer dynamics already powerfully shape goal orientations.

Third, the non-significant contribution of parental motivational climate ($r = .197$, $p = .063$; $\beta = .114$ in regression, $p = .046$) diverges from numerous Western studies documenting robust parental influence on goal orientation during adolescence (White et al., 1998; O'Rourke et al., 2014). However, this pattern aligns with longitudinal research by Keegan et al. (2014) demonstrating a marked decline in parental motivational influence as athletes transition from the sampling stage to the specialization and investment stages of athletic development. Athletes in the present sample aged 16–24, competing at intercollegiate level are likely operating within a developmental phase where autonomy from parental guidance is increasing and peer relationships carry greater social weight. Socio-cultural factors specific to Pakistani collegiate sport, where formal athletic pathways are predominantly institution-based

and coaches mediate most competitive access, may further attenuate the functional relevance of parental motivational input at this stage.

The sport discipline differences observed for coaching and peer motivational climates and achievement goal orientation underscore the importance of contextual specificity. Hockey athletes perceived significantly higher coaching climate, potentially reflecting sport-specific traditions of highly directive coaching in Pakistan (hockey being a historically prominent national sport). Volleyball athletes showed the highest peer climate and achievement goal scores, which may reflect the cooperative and interdependent nature of the sport itself, where peer feedback during play is structurally embedded. These patterns caution against assuming uniform motivational dynamics across sport types and support calls for sport-specific intervention design.

The absence of age and experience effects on any study variable is noteworthy but not surprising given the relatively restricted age range and experience range of the sample. The absence of any sport type (team vs. individual) and parental background effects suggests that macro-level structural categorizations may be less predictive of motivational orientation than the quality of specific social relationships.

CONCLUSION

This study provides compelling evidence that peer motivational climate is the predominant social determinant of achievement goal orientation among male college-level athletes in Lahore, Pakistan, accounting for nearly three-quarters of the variance in achievement goal orientation when examined alongside parental and coaching influences. Coaching motivational climate was not a significant predictor and its directional influence warrants further examination. Parental influence, while marginal in the multivariate context, was not trivial and should not be dismissed in intervention planning. These findings bear implications for how sport institutions structure motivational environments and direct professional development resources for coaches and parents.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- **Peer-Centered Intervention Programs:** Given the primacy of peer motivational climate, sport psychologists and administrators should design structured peer leadership programs within teams, training athletes to articulate task-involving norms emphasizing improvement, effort, and cooperative learning and to minimize ego-involving dynamics such as intra-team rivalry and normative comparison.
- **Coach Education:** The non-significant and directionally negative coaching climate effect identifies an urgent need for systematic coach education in motivational climate design. Workshops grounded in TARGET principles (Task, Authority, Recognition, Grouping, Evaluation, Timing; Ames, 1992) should be mandated at the college athletic program level to equip coaches with evidence-based strategies for cultivating task-involving training environments.
- **Sport Psychologist Appointments:** College athletic program should consider appointing trained sport psychologists to address athletes' goal-setting competencies.

Evidence-based goal-setting training embedded within the competitive season rather than administered as isolated workshops would better align with the dynamic motivational pressures athletes encounter.

- **Parent Engagement:** Although parental influence was attenuated in this sample, targeted parent orientation sessions that communicate the value of task-involving encouragement (emphasizing effort, enjoyment, and personal improvement over outcome-based pressure) remain advisable for younger or early-stage athletes.
- **Future Research Directions:** Longitudinal designs would enable tracking of changes in the relative influence of parents, coaches, and peers across athletic career stages. Research encompassing female athletes, university level populations, and comparison across provinces (Punjab vs. Sindh) would enhance generalizability. Incorporating mediating variables such as basic psychological need satisfaction and sport-related anxiety would further illuminate mechanisms underlying the peer climate goal orientation relationship.

LIMITATIONS

Several limitations must be acknowledged. The study was cross-sectional, precluding causal inference. The sample was restricted to male athletes in Lahore District, limiting generalizability to female athletes, rural settings, and other provinces. The relatively small sample size ($N = 90$) reduces statistical power for detecting small effect sizes. Proportionate sampling from five colleges introduces clustering effects that were not modeled analytically. Self-report measures are subject to social desirability bias, and no observational or objective measure of coaching or peer behavior was included. Replication with larger, more diverse samples and mixed-methods approaches would strengthen confidence in these findings.

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